

EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION FOR LEADERSHIP

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In today's business world, effective communication is crucial for success. Therefore, it is essential for all members of a business organization to have strong communication skills. For leaders, this skill becomes even more critical. A leader's communication abilities directly impact the organization's success or failure, influencing everything from its progress and work efficiency to policy-making and decision outcomes.

In my presentation, I will highlight several notable leaders and their leadership qualities. I will also discuss valuable lessons we can learn from their lives, struggles, and successes. By examining their examples, we can glean insights into the qualities and values needed to achieve success in our own endeavours.

I have chosen a selection of leaders from both the past and present who have pioneered change, driven social reform, or contributed to the establishment of major institutions. These leaders have inspired people through their exemplary work and made significant impacts on the lives of ordinary people. They have made their mark in various fields such as education, business, politics, and society by confronting injustices, ignorance, and exploitation. Their success stemmed from their exceptional leadership qualities, including empathy, imagination, positive thinking, vision, insight, and fearlessness. Through their examples, I will highlight the essential qualities and skills that leaders need today to effectively lead and manage organizations, educational institutions, or social enterprises. I will examine excerpts from their speeches that reflect their vision and leadership qualities, showcasing their roles as sources of inspiration and exemplary leaders. Let's explore what it truly takes to be a leader.

I would first like to discuss Martin Luther King Jr., who campaigned tirelessly for racial equality in America. King revitalized the struggle for dignity and respect for African Americans who faced severe exploitation and humiliation. One of his most famous speeches poignantly illustrates his resolve and determination.

He stated: **America has given the Negro people a bad check, a check which has come back marked 'insufficient funds.' But we refuse to believe that the bank of justice is bankrupt. We refuse to believe that there are insufficient funds in the great vaults of opportunity of this nation. So we've come to cash this check, a check that will give us upon demand the riches of freedom and the security of justice. We have come to this hallowed spot to remind America of the fierce urgency of now. I have a dream that my four little children will one day live in a nation where they will not be judged by the color of their skin but by the content of their character. I have a dream.**¹

King's speech reflects his strong faith, hope, and ability to mobilize people toward action. His words ignited hope and confidence in the hearts of many and inspired them to strive for an America where equality and freedom prevail. This speech demonstrates that a great leader should possess a clear vision and the ability to connect with and inspire others.

Another remarkable leader was Swami Vivekananda, an Indian philosopher, spiritual guide, and social reformer. He played a vital role in introducing Vedanta and Yoga to the Western world. His teachings emphasized the universality of all religions and the unity of humanity. His influential speech at the 1893 World Parliament of Religions in Chicago began with:

Sisters and Brothers of America, it fills my heart with joy unspeakable to rise in response to the warm and cordial welcome which you have given us. I thank you in the name of the most ancient order of monks in the world; I thank you... I thank you in the name of the mother of religions, and I thank you in the name of millions and millions of Hindu people of all classes and sects. I am proud to belong to a religion which has taught the world both tolerance and universal acceptance.²

Vivekananda's address highlighted empathy and tolerance, essential traits for any leader. His use of inclusive language like "sisters and brothers" helped forge a bond with his audience, earning their admiration and respect. This example teaches us that a leader should have a broad outlook and demonstrate empathy and discipline based on core principles. India was fortunate to have Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, a visionary thinker who reformed Hindu society by advocating for the abolition of untouchability and promoting equality. His efforts

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gave a voice to the Dalits and secured them rights and reservations in education and employment.

He famously stated: **Some men say that they should be satisfied with the abolition of untouchability only, leaving the caste system alone. The aim of abolition of untouchability alone without trying to abolish the inequalities inherent in the caste system is a rather low aim. Not failure, but low aim is a crime... If disease is not rightly diagnosed, the remedy will be useless and the cure may be delayed. I have hopes that my countrymen will someday learn that the country is greater than men.**³

Dr. Ambedkar's commitment to social justice is reflected in the Indian Constitution he drafted, which remains a robust framework for safeguarding the rights of all citizens. His life teaches us that pioneering leaders not only generate innovative ideas but also navigate complex challenges with creative solutions.

Sir Sayyad Ahmed Khan made significant contributions to education and the upliftment of the Muslim community in India. He established the Aligarh Muslim University in 1920, promoting modern education despite facing considerable opposition. His dedication is evident from his speech at the foundation of MAO College: **Oh my dear children, you had reached a particular stage, and remember one thing that when I undertook the task, there was criticism all around against me, and abuses upon me. Life had become so difficult for me that I aged before my age. I lost my hair, my eyesight, but not my vision. My vision never dimmed; my determination never failed. I built this institution for you, and I am sure you will carry the light of this institution far and wide; darkness will disappear from all around.**⁴

Sir Syed's efforts in education and his advocacy for the Urdu language highlight his belief in the power of education and cultural unity. His legacy continues through the institutions he established and his impact on societal progress. A true leader must have unwavering faith in their mission and demonstrate perseverance and patience.

In the business world, Narayan Murthy, the founder of Infosys, stands out for revolutionizing the Indian IT sector. Infosys has become one of the largest companies in the industry, with an annual turnover of about 40,000 crores. In his speech, Murthy said: **It is a unified multitude and not a mere group of people. As it is said in the Vedas: Man can live individually, but can survive only collectively. Hence, the challenge is to form a progressive community by balancing the interests of the individual and that of the society. To meet this, we need to develop a value system where people accept modest sacrifices for the common good...**

There are two pillars of the cultural value system - loyalty to family and loyalty to community. One should not be in isolation to the other because successful societies are those which combine both harmoniously.⁵

Murthy's commitment to both business innovation and philanthropy demonstrates that effective leadership encompasses not only professional success but also a dedication to social welfare and community progress. His approach to leadership highlights the importance of innovation, motivation, and empowering others.

Abraham Lincoln, the 16th President of the United States, profoundly influenced American history through his leadership during the Civil War and his fight against slavery. Despite lacking formal education, his leadership qualities were exemplary.

In his famous Gettysburg Address, Lincoln declared: **Four score and seven years ago our fathers brought forth, on this continent, a new nation, conceived in Liberty, and dedicated to the proposition that all men are created equal. Now we are engaged in a great civil war, testing whether that nation, or any nation so conceived and so dedicated, can long endure... We here highly resolve that these dead shall not have died in vain—that this nation, under God, shall have a new birth of freedom—and that government of the people, by the people, for the people, shall not perish from the earth.⁶**

Lincoln's communication style was both assertive and empathetic. He effectively conveyed his goals and values, fostering an environment where open dialogue was encouraged. His example teaches us that great leaders should be compassionate, democratic, and open to diverse perspectives. We can conclude that to be successful communicator one needs a vision for the progress of all, an idea that can be transformed into reality. The examples of the leaders we discussed demonstrate that effective communication is a crucial tool for leaders in driving change, inspiring people, and shaping the course of history. By embodying qualities such as clarity, empathy, vision, ethical leadership, and a commitment to social justice, these leaders have left an indelible mark on the world. Such individuals remain an inspiration in our journey to develop communication skills.

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